

**TEACHING ENGLISH PRE-INTERMEDIATE LEVEL PSYCHOLOGY
STUDENTS' USING THE CLIL METHOD**

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Annotation: This article discusses the implementation of the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) method in teaching English to pre-intermediate level psychology students. The CLIL approach integrates psychology content into English language lessons, promoting language acquisition by a meaningful context. The article highlights the effectiveness of using CLIL, including the development of cognitive skills, active student interaction and collaboration. It provides different examples of teaching activities, such as reading psychology articles, engaging in case studies, role-plays, group projects, and authentic listening activities. The CLIL method not only enhances language proficiency but also deepens students' comprehension of psychology principles and theories, preparing them for academic and professional success.

Key words: CLIL, enhancing, problem solving, case study, collaboration, psychology

**CLIL METODIDAN FOYDALANIB PRE-INTERMEDIATE
DARAJADAGI PSIXOLOGIYA TALABALARIGA INGLIZ TILINI
O'QITISH.**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) usulini pre-intermediate darajadagi psixologiya talabalariga ingliz tilini o'rgatishdat tatbiq etilishi muhokama qilinadi. CLIL yondashuvi psixologiya fan mazmunini ingliz tili darslariga birlashtiradi va mazmunli kontekstda tilni o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Maqolada CLILdan foydalanishning afzalliklari, jumladan, kognitiv qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish, talabalarning faol ishtiroki va hamkorlikda ishlash kabilar haqida so'z yuritiladi. U psixologiyaga oid maqolalarni o'qish, amaliy tadqiqotlar, rolli o'yinlar va guruh loyihalari faoliyati kabi o'qitish faoliyatining turli misollarini taqdim etadi. CLIL usuli nafaqat tilni bilish darajasini oshiradi, balki talabalarning psixologiya tamoyillari va nazariyalari haqidagi tushunchalarini chuqurlashtiradi, ularni akademik va kasbiy muvaffaqiyatga tayyorlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar:CLIL, sifatini oshirmoq, muammoni yechish, keys stadi, hamkorlik.

English language proficiency has become an important skill in today's globalized world, and its value extends beyond the realm of linguistics. In disciplines such as psychology, where students are required to engage with complex theories, research, and academic discourse, proficiency in English becomes crucial. To cater to the specific needs of pre-intermediate level psychology students, the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) method provides a comprehensive approach to teaching English while simultaneously improving subject-specific knowledge. This article explores the benefits and strategies of using the CLIL method to teach English to pre-intermediate level psychology students.

The CLIL method involves integrating content from different subject areas with language learning objectives, ensuring that language acquisition takes place within a meaningful context. By incorporating psychology-related materials, discussions, and tasks into English language lessons, students are exposed to both the language and concepts of the sphere. This approach not only improves their English language skills but also enhances their understanding of psychology principles and theories. The

primary goal of CLIL is to create an immersive and interactive environment that fosters language development while promoting subject knowledge acquisition.

The CLIL method offers a wide range of teaching activities that can be used to integrate psychology content into English language lessons for pre-intermediate level students. These activities aim to create an immersive and interactive environment that enhances language proficiency while promoting subject knowledge acquisition. Here are some examples of teaching activities that can be implemented using the CLIL approach [Ball Ph.207,p5]:

- Reading and analyzing psychology articles;
- Case studies and problem-solving tasks;
- Role-plays and simulations;
- Group projects and presentations;
- Vocabulary building activities;
- Authentic listening and video activities.

These teaching activities not only promote language acquisition but also foster a deeper understanding of psychology principles and theories. By integrating psychology content into English language lessons, students can develop their language skills while engaging with the subject matter in a meaningful and authentic way. The CLIL approach ensures that language learning takes place within a relevant context, preparing students to effectively communicate and comprehend psychology concepts in their academic and professional pursuits.

The CLIL method offers an excellent opportunity to develop cognitive skills in pre-intermediate psychology students while simultaneously improving their English language proficiency. By engaging with authentic materials and engaging in higher-order thinking processes, students can enhance their critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical abilities. Here is a more detailed explanation of how the CLIL method promotes cognitive skill development, along with examples of activities that can be implemented:

Critical Thinking: CLIL encourages students to analyze and evaluate complex psychological concepts and materials. This fosters their ability to think critically and make reasoned judgments. For example:

- Provide students with a research article on a controversial topic in psychology, such as the nature vs. nurture debate.
- Ask students to identify and evaluate the arguments presented in the article, considering the evidence and logical reasoning.
- Engage students in a class discussion where they can express their opinions, challenge assumptions, and defend their viewpoints.

2. Problem Solving: Psychology often involves the application of theories and concepts to real-life situations. CLIL enables students to develop problem-solving skills by engaging with case studies and practical scenarios.

For example:

- Present students with a case study involving a psychological disorder or a specific problem in interpersonal relationships.
- Ask students to analyze the case study, identify the underlying issues, and propose possible solutions or interventions.
- Encourage students to consider multiple perspectives and use psychological theories and principles to support their recommendations.

3. Analysis: CLIL exposes students to authentic materials, such as research papers and scholarly articles, which require them to analyze and interpret complex information. For example:

- Assign students a research article that explores a specific psychological phenomenon, such as cognitive biases.
- Ask students to analyze the methodology, results, and conclusions of the study.
- Engage students in a group discussion where they can critically assess the strengths and limitations of the research, as well as its implications.

4. Comparing and Contrasting: CLIL provides opportunities for students to compare and contrast different psychological theories, perspectives, or research findings. This helps them develop their analytical skills and see connections between different concepts. For example:

- Assign students to compare and contrast two theories of personality, such as the psychodynamic and humanistic perspectives.
- Ask students to identify the key similarities and differences between the theories, considering their underlying assumptions and implications.
- Have students present their findings in a structured manner, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of each theory.

5. Data Analysis: Psychology often involves analyzing and interpreting data. CLIL allows students to develop their data analysis skills by engaging with research studies and statistical information. For example:

- Provide students with a set of data related to a psychological experiment or survey.
- Ask students to analyze the data, identify patterns or trends, and draw appropriate conclusions.
- Guide students in presenting their findings using appropriate statistical language and visual representations, such as charts or graphs. [Meyer O.20 0,p 6]

By engaging in these types of cognitive activities within the CLIL framework, pre-intermediate psychology students can sharpen their critical thinking, problem solving, and analytical skills. These skills are essential not only for their academic success but also for their future careers in psychology or related fields. The CLIL method ensures that students are not only learning English but also developing the cognitive abilities necessary to thrive in their academic and professional endeavors.

Moreover, the CLIL method encourages active student participation and collaboration. Rather than relying solely on teacher-entered instruction, CLIL fosters a learner-centered approach that emphasizes interaction, discussion, and group work. Students engage in conversations, debates, and presentations, allowing them to apply

their language skills in authentic situations. By working collaboratively, students also benefit from peer-to-peer learning as they exchange ideas, clarify concepts, and offer constructive feedback to one another.

This collaborative environment not only enhances language proficiency but also promotes social and communication skills, which are vital for future psychologists.

Furthermore, the CLIL approach taps into students' intrinsic motivation by connecting language learning with their field of study. Traditional language instruction often focuses on unrelated, abstract topics that may not resonate with students' interests or future career paths. By integrating psychology content into language lessons, CLIL creates a meaningful learning experience that is relevant and engaging. Students are more likely to be motivated to learn English when they can see the direct application of their language skills in their chosen field. This intrinsic motivation fosters a positive learning environment, encouraging students to take ownership of their language learning journey.

In conclusion, the CLIL method offers a comprehensive and effective approach to teaching English to pre-intermediate level psychology students. By integrating content from the field of psychology into language lessons, CLIL provides students with an immersive and meaningful learning experience. The method not only enhances language proficiency but also develops cognitive skills, promotes collaboration, facilitates domain-specific language acquisition, and fosters intrinsic motivation.

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